

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SPACED LEARNING METHOD INTO TEACHING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the importance of strengthening memory which is the main factor in effective learning process. The language learning is both sophisticated and interesting process that helps learners obtain new knowledge, broaden a horizon, boost language acquisition and gift new opportunities for their future career. The article gives information about challenges that occur while learning L2 language that can be overcome owing to innovative methods including "Spaced learning".

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МЕТОДА ПРОСТРАНСТВЕННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

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ABSTRACT

В этой статье подчеркивается важность укрепления памяти, которая является основным фактором эффективного процесса обучения. Изучение языка — это одновременно сложный и интересный процесс, который помогает учащимся получить новые знания, расширить кругозор, ускорить овладение языком и открыть новые возможности для будущей карьеры. В статье представлена информация о трудностях, возникающих при изучении языка L2, которые можно преодолеть благодаря инновационным методам, в том числе «Разнесенному обучению».

TA'LIM JARAYONINDA FAZOVIIY O'QITISH USULINING TADBIQ ETILISHI

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqola samarali ta'lim jarayonining asosiy omili bo'lgan xotirani mustahkamlash muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Til o'rganish murakkab va qiziqarli jarayon bo'lib, u o'quvchilarga yangi bilim olish, dunyoqarashini kengaytirish, tilni o'zlashtirishni kuchaytirish va kelajakdagi martaba uchun yangi imkoniyatlarni taqdim etishda yordam beradi. Maqolada L2 tilini o'rganishda yuzaga keladigan qiyinchiliklar haqida ma'lumot berilgan, ularni innovatsion usullar, shu jumladan "Interval bilan o'rganish" yordamida yengib o'tish mumkin.

Nowadays one of the actual problem of mankind is a problem associated with a memory, to be more exact, with a memorization of a given information. What is a memory itself? Memory is a complex system based on the numerous processes in the brain. This is the ability to remember and save information as well as reproduce it if necessary. Therefore, we can say that memory is an important part of our life. If we lost our memory, we would have to learn everything from scratch. In order to keep our memory in a good shape, we must take care of it by training our brain.(Anohin, 1968) Hence everyone is looking for an answer to the question of how to reinforce our brain and make it remember a significant material not for a week or a month, but forever.

In order to reveal an appropriate answer to this issue lots of scholars, psychologists made their researches, explorations on this project. Ultimately, after a long-term investigations, one of the scholars, whose name was Paul Kelley, was able to design and develop the method which is called Spaced learning.

Spaced learning is a new and innovative method of teaching in which the same learning content is reiterated three times with a ten-minute interval and while this interval students have to do various activities, exercises in order to give the brain an opportunity to relax. (Fields, 2005) We can get acquainted closer with the Spaced learning method, exactly with advantageous of this platform in a teaching process and its possible future results through Sean H.K. Kang's article. According to his point of view, Kang (2016) claims that the implementation of spaced learning into teaching process reinforces and proliferates students' consciousness toward the information that they have been given. Spaced practice is both enforceable and very effective method to which is able to boost students' potential to get higher results from their education. (Kang, 2016). If someone wants to memorize a learning material, frequently, this material is considered as temporal, but not permanent. (Kang, 2016) As Kang (2016) highlights that "Practice makes perfect", learners have to make more practice than approaching to the theme theoretically. In this case they will manage to register the learning material forever.

According to my own observations, I revealed that after working on myself, and doing lots of practice I have noticed that my awareness toward languages and other subjects (math,

economy and etc.) has been improved in a very short period of time. From this follows that everything can be achieved only through practice. Therefore, a very benefit of spaced learning is that is based on practical affairs. (Kang, 2016). Instead of repeating one material in a short period of time, it will be better to replicate it some intervals later. This procedure is called a Spaced effect and was firstly investigated several centuries ago (Ebbinghaus, 1885/1913). Since this centuries, many psychologists have held experiments which indicate to the advantages of spaced or distributed practice (Cepeda et al., 2006).

In order to distinguish an effectiveness of spaced practice from massed practice, Kang (2016) has created a graphical representation of this process, to figure out the prons of spacing procedure which is shown below.

There were held some experiments to compare spaced practice and massed practice. The results of research exposed that the second approach had collapsed (Cepeda et al., 2006). To prove the statement which is given above Gordon (1925) exemplified the situation where a collage teacher gave the task to students to learn about the Athenian Oath. According to this test, 50 % of students were listening to the word “oath” read six times successively(massed repetition), and another 50% had heard it in one day three times and three days later three more times (spaced practice). As an experiment exposed that the students, who had used

spaced repetition, were able to remember the word “oath” effortlessly compared to the users of massed reiteration (Rawsan and Kintsch, 2005).

What is a massed learning? Massed learning is a method when students intensively learn one information without gap (Collins Dictionary). Sometimes this type of learning can seem more advantageous than spaced practice for remembering the information for the short period of time, but the spaced learning can provide learners with a long-term memorization (Rawsom and Kintsch, 2005).

Recently a very interesting theory has been put forward to prove the effectiveness of the spaced learning. According to this theory, people in order to memorize something they have to forget it (Carey, 2010)

Are the flashcards are beneficial in spaced learning? As Kornell (2009) says that the implementation of flashcards is a very effective way to conduct the lesson and using “clickers” in order to register students’ answers to the questions of teachers can soar students’ comprehension and improve their learning proficiency.(Anderson et.al., 2013). Furthermore, there are some apps to maintain the spaced learning:

1. Eidetic
2. Memrise
3. SuperMemo
4. Quizlet and others which can be useful in memorizing of important materials.

One of the differential side of spaced learning is to amplify a memory and develop a robust thinking (Mayer, 2002). As an example Bird (2010) claims that spaced learning can not only boost learners’ mathematical skills and the ability to understand and learn scientific conceptions, but also this method helps adult learners keep in mind an English grammar permanently. Moreover, he says that the brain functions very well since it is able to not only memorize some resolutions, but also retrieve appropriate solutions to the problems.

There are enough justifications which maintain an effectiveness of spaced learning to raise educational upshots. In case if the spaced learning is included into educational system, there will be an educational productiveness because there will be no need to reiterate one thing that has been already learnt again and again, instead students can move to another more significant themes. But the utilization of this method is rare in classrooms show the psychological observations (Depster, 1988).

Taking everything into consideration, every teacher has to integrate in their lessons the spaced learning method owing to its effectiveness and lots of advantageous (James, 1899). For instance, the students who carried the national examination on 30 January 2009, due to the spaced practice, were able to pass their exam felicitously. (Kelley). Thus, every pedagogue should think about the perfect ways to form a spaced learning process not only inside the classrooms, but also out of it. (Kang, 2016).

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